

Connecting the Opens (III): Navigating the challenges on the path to openness in Higher Education

Connecting the Opens leadership series | 3

This third item in the series continues exploring how university leaders across Europe are connecting Open Science and Open Education. Based on interviews conducted by SPARC Europe, the series aims to inspire more leaders to connect the opens and support institutions in addressing complex challenges through an integrated open knowledge framework.

The challenges of moving toward openness

For university leaders committed to connecting open research, open education, and societal engagement, translating that vision into practice means navigating a complex landscape of deeply rooted academic norms and habits, commercial pressures, and institutional issues. Naming these challenges is the first step toward addressing them with purpose and confidence. These conditions do not prevent openness from advancing, but they require thoughtful adaptation and leadership.

The experience of many institutions shows that the transition toward openness involves addressing several interconnected challenges. These relate not only to infrastructure and policy, but also to the commodification of knowledge, incentives, culture, awareness, and the broader knowledge ecosystem in which universities operate. Understanding these challenges helps institutions move from isolated initiatives to a coherent, sustainable open strategy.

The key challenges in advancing openness are:

Policy alignment and national context: The broader policy environment also shapes the pace of openness. Differences in national strategies for open education, in particular, funding frameworks and government awareness influence institutional priorities and support structures.

Strengthening dialogue among universities, funders and policymakers helps ensure that open practices are supported by coherent national and international frameworks.

Commercial structures within scholarly communication: The wider research ecosystem has developed around publishing and licensing models that are often driven by the increasing commercialisation of science, and prioritise restricted access, which is in direct conflict with openness. Proprietary platforms, licensing agreements and copyright limitations and the influence of some commercial actors are limiting the transition toward more open knowledge systems. The lobbying efforts of large textbook publishers to maintain their existing business models also present a considerable obstacle. Certain universities, in the light of cost-cutting and revenue-generation efforts, can seem somewhat challenged by the open education model despite its widespread adoption.

Universities, therefore, face the challenge of overcoming apathy to the status quo, navigating existing commercial relationships while gradually strengthening open alternatives, shared infrastructures and more sustainable models of knowledge dissemination, whilst also embracing more equity in access to information.

As stated by one expert:

“The underlying issue of donating time, labour, and public funds to create knowledge and then relinquishing control to businesses that limit access remains a core challenge.”

Academic incentives and reward systems: One of the most frequently cited challenges, and probably the most fundamental one, relates to the lack of alignment between open practices and the highly competitive academic reward and recognition systems that focus more on individual achievement than collaboration. Career progression in many institutions continues to rely heavily on citation metrics, journal prestige and publication counts.

As stated by another expert:

“Most metrics used are for short-term evaluations, whereas openness in science offers a better diffusion and quality of science in the long-term”

Clarity and shared understanding of openness: Openness encompasses a range of practices, including open science, open education, open data and open infrastructures. Across institutions and disciplines, these concepts are sometimes interpreted differently. Gaining penetration within subject communities and convincing faculty to engage with open practices requires significant advocacy and practical guidance.

This diversity reflects the movement's evolving nature, but it can also create uncertainty about what openness means in practice. Developing a shared institutional understanding based on internationally agreed policy, such as the UNESCO Recommendations for Open Science and OER, or on national policy, and focusing on advocacy and concrete support help provide clearer direction and confidence for faculty and staff adopting open approaches.

Institutional infrastructure and capacity: Many leaders, researchers and educators express a strong interest in working openly but may lack the practical support required to do so effectively. Open practices depend on reliable repositories, metadata systems, digital tools, and specialised staff who can support data management, licensing and open publishing, and time needs to be made available to use and create open content.

Building and maintaining this infrastructure requires long-term investment and coordination across institutional units such as libraries, IT services and research offices; sharing more services is the future.

Skills and professional development: Implementing open practices often requires new competencies, particularly in digital tools, copyright and licensing, data management, and collaborative pedagogies. Many academic staff have learned these practices informally, often with support from libraries and open knowledge advocates.

Strengthening training opportunities and professional development programmes can significantly accelerate the practical implementation of openness across institutions.

Activities such as sharing research data, developing Open Educational Resources (OER), collaborating openly across institutions, or engaging with society are not always equally recognised in promotion and evaluation processes. Aligning incentives with institutional values around openness, therefore, remains an important step in accelerating adoption.

Adoption and use of open educational resources: The growing availability of open learning materials presents new opportunities for teaching and learning. At the same time, institutions face practical questions around discoverability, quality assurance, localisation, and the time required for academic staff to adapt and create resources.

Encouraging the reuse and co-creation of Open Educational Resources across institutions can help address these issues while building stronger collaborative academic communities.

Ethical and legal considerations: Some disciplines face specific concerns when sharing research outputs openly. Issues related to personal data, research ethics, knowledge security or sensitive datasets require careful management.

Developing responsible open practices that balance transparency with ethical, legal, security and privacy obligations is essential to advancing openness in research and education.

Universities and colleges are learning how to adapt their structures to a more open knowledge environment.

In summary, as stated by one leader:

“The large-scale adoption of open education is hindered by issues at strategic, tactical, and operational levels, including challenges related to business models, awareness of open formats, insufficient strategic vision, copyright and licensing complexities, a lack of digital skills among staff, the findability and quality of OER, human factors like reluctance to share, unclear incentives, and concerns about the loss of regional identity and the impact on accreditation processes.”

Universities that invest in infrastructure, align incentives, strengthen training and build shared understanding are increasingly able to connect their open science and open education initiatives more effectively.

It is essential to bridge the “apathy gap” and overcome resistance to openness, and by reviewing the commercialisation of the Higher Education Sector.

As openness becomes more embedded in institutional strategies, these efforts will help universities realise the broader vision of accessible, collaborative and socially engaged knowledge systems.

Following the previous item exploring the [drivers of openness in higher education](#), this piece has examined the key challenges institutions navigate when connecting open research, open education and societal engagement. These insights are grounded in our [Connecting the Opens Position Paper](#).

In the next item of the series, we will explore how university leaders are developing concrete institutional strategies to strengthen these connections and embed openness across their institutions.

5 key actions

- 1. Acknowledge and strategically navigate the commercial and competitive landscape:** Recognise the inherent conflicts arising from the commodification of research and the competitive academic reward system that can disincentivise openness. Emphasise the need for proactive strategies to mitigate the influence of proprietary interests and to foster a culture that values collaboration and open sharing.
- 2. Reform reward and incentive structures to recognise open contributions:** Underscore the critical misalignment between current academic reward systems (focused on traditional metrics) and the values and activities of open scholarship. Advocate for a fundamental shift in tenure and promotion guidelines to explicitly recognise and value contributions such as open data sharing, OER creation, and public engagement.
- 3. Address the lack of clarity and unified understanding of "open":** Highlight the existing ambiguity surrounding the definition and scope of open scholarship and open education. Advocate for the development of clear institutional frameworks and definitions to provide guidance and promote consistent adoption across disciplines and departments.
- 4. Invest in infrastructure and support to overcome practical implementation challenges:** Recognise that the outsourcing of scholarly communication infrastructure and the lack of internal expertise create significant barriers to implementing open practices. Emphasise the need for strategic investments in infrastructure, training, and dedicated support staff to empower faculty and students to engage effectively with open science and open education.
- 5. Proactively address concerns around quality, misinformation, and intellectual property:** Acknowledge the legitimate concerns surrounding the quality of open resources, the potential for the spread of misinformation, and faculty uncertainty regarding open licences and intellectual property. Emphasise the need for robust quality assurance mechanisms, clear guidelines on licensing, and educational initiatives to address these concerns and build trust in open practices.

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